

**PARADOX: A THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UNDERSTANDING
POSTCOLONIAL TEXTS**

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ABSTRACT :

Reading a postcolonial text is always a challenge in the sense that it is highly discussive in nature. This text has a tendency to get overlapped into cultural, historical, social, linguistics, psychological, national, ideological and geographical boundaries and thus confronts a reader from multiple fronts. Thus, reading of such a text will need a flexible theoretical framework, accommodative to and considerate of, as far as possible, all the differences that the reader encounters while reading. A sample framework can be conceived in terms of a paradox which will have the elements of Deconstruction, Psychoanalysis (Lacanian model), Neo-Marxism (as in Althusser and Gramsci) and Post-colonial theories. The aim of this paper is to study the perspectives in reference so as to draw a theoretical framework as paradox, from them to throw light on reading and understanding of postcolonial texts, with reference to V.S. Naipaul. The paper argues that the origin and destination of this proposed framework is paradoxical in nature which can considerably leverage the understanding of a postcolonial writer like Naipaul.

Key Words: paradox, Deconstruction, Psychoanalysis, Marxism, Postcolonial

INTRODUCTION :

Etymologically, the term paradox is derived from the Greek word “paradoxon” which means a “contrary” opinion or situation. According to the Oxford online dictionary, it means “a seemingly absurd or contradictory statement”ⁱ that on investigation might have logical conclusion. It also means that it is a situation leading “to a conclusion that seems logically unacceptable or self-contradictory.”ⁱⁱ It might further mean that “a person or thing that combines contradictory features or qualities.”ⁱⁱⁱ In other words, the dimension of the paradox may extend up to statements, situations, persons and things in which literature/literary criticism are no exceptions. In literary criticism it is Cleanth Brooks, the New Critic, who had suspected the poetic use of language was simple and straightforward. For him, the language of poetry is the language of paradox. In the very opening line of his essay ‘The Language of Paradox (1956)’ he writes, “Few of us are prepared to the statement that the language of poetry is the language of paradox...Yet there is a sense in which paradox is the language appropriate and inevitable to poetry” (Brooks 58). In other words, irony, metaphor, ambiguity, symbols, image, strangeness, suspense, double and contrast etc. or the figures of speech based on indirectness, which are the very integral parts of poetic language can be understood from the perspective of paradox in Brooks. In course of elaboration and on the question of where Wordsworth’s sonnet ‘Composed upon Westminster Bridge’ gets its power from, he writes, “It gets it, it seems to me, from the paradoxical situation out of which the poem arises” (Brooks 59). John Danvers in his seminal book *Picturing Mind Paradox, Indeterminacy and Consciousness in Art and Poetry* (2006) sees a possibility of “a convergence between science and art” (Danvers 17), a paradox, as far as some of the schemes of both are only an approximation of events and happenings that constitute reality. Linking arts to “mystical”, “a body of ideas about state of being and knowing” (Danvers 261) of the world he affirms that, It may be possible to consider some kinds of art and poetry as modes of pointing, showing or demonstrating how the world is- through metaphor, paradoxical language, poetic images or forms of visual/spatial representations (Danvers 284).

It is in these models- Brooks and Danvers-as an artistic pointer, the paradox has been understood and engaged with as a “showing” device with a conviction that the show will enable a deeper exploration and understanding of “how the world is.” However, as far as the nature of the postcolonial texts, as

can be seen in the works of V.S. Naipaul, are concerned, these understandings will be inadequate and thus need consideration of other dimensions of paradox as well which are discussed as below.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To explore the philosophical dimension of the paradox;
2. To explore Derridean dimension of the paradox;
3. To explore Lacanian dimension of the paradox;
4. To explore postcolonial dimension of the paradox.

PHILOSOPHICAL PARADOX :

The paradox also has extensively sensed the modern philosophy/ philosophical studies as a point of departure from the conventional ideas. For modernist like Friedrich Nietzsche, paradox is an existential situation for existence. His paradoxical thinking underlines his work like *The Birth of Tragedy* (1872) and *Will to Power* (1901). Tracing the birth of tragedy in early Greece, he frames the dichotomy of the concepts “Apollonian” and “Dionysian”, alluding to the Greek god of intellect and wisdom, Apollo, for the first, and the God of wine and intoxication, Dionysus, for the second, which emerges as a paradoxical tension in the nature of early Greek tragedy. The highest form of the Greek tragedies, as in Sophocles (*Oedipus Rex*, for instance) and Aeschylus (*Agamemnon*, for instance), take birth from the constitution of the paradoxical dichotomy. Nietzsche thus links paradox to aesthetics to arrive at the source of human tragedy. In *Will to Power*, he observes source of nihilism in reason, that is to say too much faith in reason will lead to the state of nothingness, a supreme paradox. He says, “The faith in the categories of reason is the cause of nihilism” (Nietzsche 13). In relation to the cause of nihilism, he asks “What does nihilism mean? And answers, it is a state where “...the highest values devalue themselves” (Nietzsche 9). It implies that even the “highest values”, the highly regarded knowledge system, religion for instance, in other words have an inherent paradoxical tendency to nullify itself. This paradox, however, has other interpretations in the Twentieth century, explored as follows.

DERRIDEAN PARADOX :

In the latter half of the Twentieth century Derridean thought leverages academics and philosophy. Jacques Derrida first decodes a paradoxical situation in linguistics to show a sustained suspended union between a “signifier” and its “signified,” word as sign and its signification in *Of Grammatology* (1967) and gradually penetrates philosophy as in *Margins of Philosophy* (1972) and *Spectres of Marx* (1993). Dissemination of his ideas gradually triggers many of the post-structuralist theories having deconstructive modes of operation across disciplines-literature, history and psychology. Reading of Said in *Orientalism*, Stephen Greenblatt in New Historicism, Ranajit Guha in Subaltern theory, Jacques Lacan in Psychoanalysis, Helene Cixous and Julia Kristeva as psycho feminists, for instance, all have stamp of Derridian thought in their theoretical framework. Derrida along with his legacy (the ‘Yale gang of four’) – Paul de Man (for instance in *Blindness and Insight*), Geoffrey H. Hartman (*The Unremarkable Wordsworth*), J. Hillis Miller (*Fiction and Repetition: Seven English Novels*) and Harold Bloom (*The Anxiety of Influence: a Theory of Poetry*) dominates the latter half of the twentieth century critical and theoretical debates. The postcolonial theories/studies having formative influence from the *Orientalism* is also modeled also by the Derridean idea of deconstruction which therefore demands elaboration. Derrida shares the semiology of the structuralist Ferdinand de Saussure but with deviation to show his linguistic contradiction with him in regards to the relation between a “signifier” and its “signified.” For Saussure, union between the signifier, which he defines as the “sound-image...the psychological imprint of the sound, the impression that it makes in our senses” (Saussure 66) and the signified (“concept”), the two components of a “sign” which is “... the combination of a concept and a sound image...” (Saussure 66), is arbitrary:

The bond between the signifier and the signified is arbitrary. Since I mean by sign the whole that results from the associating of the signifier with the signified, I can simply say: *the linguistic sign is arbitrary* (Saussure 67).

In the arbitrariness of the relationship between the signifier and the signified, the identity of the latter, the possibility of the signifier becoming signified, is at stake. However, the term does not totally deny their impossibility; arbitrariness also implies a temporal becoming of signified. In other words, in Saussure a meaning *can be* defined in the transactional arch between the signifier and the signified; though temporary, it is a possibility. But for Derrida, the Saussurean understanding of the signifier (and also signified) is a paradox. That is to say, the arbitrary foundation of the meaning in Saussure is in fact not possible. The signifier itself is already always “representative” or derivative in origin. Thus in *Of Grammatology* (1967) he writes that the “written signifier is always technical and representative. It has no constitutive meaning. This derivation is the very origin of the notion of the ‘signifier’” (Derrida 1974, 08). It suffers an inherent tendency of self-contradiction which Derrida calls “différance” which designates both the sense of “deferring” and “differing” at the same time, a paradoxical state of nonexistent existence. The différance is not the origin or ground for being; it is only “originary”; it is “literally neither a word nor a concept” (Derrida 1972, 03). The nature of the words being so in their essence, the Western philosophy, according to Derrida, having been made too much reliant on words as mode of expression, has marginalized its scope limiting it to a centre-“logocentrism”- in the ideological discourse of a few phallogocentric thinkers like Aristotle, Descartes, Kant, Husserl, Heidegger, Spinoza, Leibniz, Hegel to name a few, and accordingly has always missed what is “beyond the philosophical text”; has failed to see how the text deconstructs itself, how it “overflows and cracks its meaning” (Derrida 1972, xxiii). The paradox of the philosophy is that, in spite of its apparent intellectual height it has ended in the same “ignorance” from which it aimed freedom; it has created a margin between its “exteriority” and interiority. Nevertheless, the philosophy in general has always concerned with its “exteriority”, an “alterity”, an “other.” Therefore, Derrida alarms an exigency just not to reproduce the logocentric philosophical discourse in “its other” forms but to bring in question the exteriority, the alterity, the “other” to break its limitation: Instead of determining some other circumscription, recognizing it, practicing it, bringing it to light, forming it, in a word producing it (and today this word serves as the crudest “new clothes” of the metaphysical denegation which accommodates itself very well to all these projects), in question will be, but according to a movement unheard of by philosophy, an ‘other’ which is no longer *its other* [form] (Derrida 1972, xiv). The “other”, thus which has a philosophical connection in Derrida has been seriously questioned in other contexts, at least in two discourses, in relation to its identity/identity formation. First is the psychoanalysis of which the Lacanian model will be more significant. Jacques Lacan offers a critique of Freudian concept of psycho-sexual development of a child through three stages- oral or the real stage, anal or the need stage and phallic or the desire stage- corresponding to its early age of development. According to Freud, the male child forms a sexual whole with the mother and the female with the father which determines their personalities. At the second stage, the child breaks the illusion of its mother (in male child, and illusion of father in the female) as a real part of life that it had taken to be in the oral stage; becomes conscious that she is different from him, that he has a separate identity, that he is another as much as she. In the final stage, the child desires to regain the sexual-whole and its identity is subject to the fulfillment/repression of this desire.

LACANIAN PARADOX :

Lacan substitutes the Freudian stages with the real, the imaginary, and the symbolic. In between the second and the last stages, there comes a short period which he calls “mirror” stage where “The child... can nevertheless already recognize as such his own image in a mirror... This act... immediately rebounds... in a series of gestures in which he experiences... the child’s own body, and the persons and things around him” (Lacan 01). This ignites a desire in the child to know the images,

which in fact is the beginning of the identity formation of him as “other” amidst other others; he is another to many others, and accordingly he adopts language as the means. However, as has been established in Derrida, the language functions only as signifier. The difference of language corresponds to his personality; human identity and the text thereafter become one. Thus, unlike Freud, the identity formation in Lacan is a site, does not necessarily correspond only to the primary stages of life; once in language domain human identity formation is a continuous process. This sense of identity-text paradox, body-text politics, in a colonial situation where English language functions as the medium of expression as in Naipaul will be of utmost importance in understanding the colonial psychology and identity formation. Secondly, the “other” has been interpreted as a racial representative of the colonized, the “orient” in the postcolonial studies where once again Naipaul will be relevant. In other words, in the Eurocentric discourse for and during the process of western colonization or “oreintalizing the orient” as Edward Said would call, the “other”, the complementary half of the western knowledge system itself, has received a racial twist: the idea is consciously transported to the colonial situation. It has been politically and strategically given an inferior racial form to re-present the colonized so as to subjugate and rule for the realization of the larger colonial goals. And therefore, it needs re-presentation, re-formation as decolonization for which a number of theories have been called for. This brings us next to the post-colonial theories to see their engagement with the “other” in their discursive practices.

MARXIST PARADOX :

Louis Althusser draws upon the idea of the classical Marxist, “base” and “superstructure,” and the idea of the economic determinism. However, unlike the classical Marxism, Althusser sees the superstructures as the agency of the bourgeoisie’s ideology; he calls them the “Ideological State Apparatus”. By ideology he means a “system of the ideas and representations which dominate the mind of a man or a social group” (Althusser 253). He identifies the Ideological State Apparatus with the religious institutions (church system), educational (private and public school system), family, legal, political (political system and parties), communication (radio, television, press etc.) and cultural (literature, arts, sports etc). The Ideological State Apparatus operates side by side with what he calls the “Repressive State Apparatus” like army, police etc; the first functions “with ideology” the latter “by violence”; the first functions in “private” domain, the later in the “public”. Both the apparatus are the agency of the ruling class ideology. Thus, in his seminal book *On the Reproduction of Capitalism: Ideology and Ideological Status Apparatus* (2014) Althusser writes: If the ISAs [Ideological State Apparatus] function' massively and predominantly by ideology... which is the ideology of ' the ruling class'. Given the fact that the ' ruling class' in principle holds state power ..., and therefore has at its disposal the (Repressive) State Apparatus, ...this same ruling class is [equally] active in the Ideological State Apparatuses insofar as it is ultimately the ruling ideology which is realized in the Ideological State Apparatuses (Althusser 245). How the ruling class ideology operates and what it ensures are yet to answer. The ideology ensures power capital but to elaborate how it operates and to what extent, we need to draw upon Gramsci, his idea of “hegemony.” Use of the hegemony in him can be traced back to his note ‘Some aspect of southern question’ in relation to the proletariat in Turin. He writes, “The Turin communists posed concretely the question of the ‘hegemony of the proletariat’: i.e. ...The proletariat can become the leading ...and the dominant class to the extent that it succeeds in creating a system of class alliances which allows it to mobilize the majority of the working population against capitalism and the bourgeois State” (Gramsci 1978, 3-4). Gramsci speaks of hegemony here as an essentialism for making proletariat ideology dominant in its mass to become “dominant” class; to assume power. Therefore, it can be assumed that the hegemony implies an ideological and cultural control and dominance over other for power. It is in *Prison Notebooks* he relates it to the ruling class, the function of the Ideological State Apparatus. He thus writes the “Unity of the State in separation of powers [Legislature, Judiciary and Executive] are also the organs of political hegemony, but in different degrees” (Gramsci 1999, 507). The ideology thus

operates in a hegemonic relationship between a dominating and dominated class and ensures power to the former.

POSTCOLONIAL PARADOX :

With Althusser and Gramsci in mind then we can recourse to the postcolonial theory which tends to act like “avant garde” against the colonial ideology and hegemony. The postcolonial theory engages in the relation between the Western empire (English, Spanish, Portuguese, German, French and of late with a difference, American) and their previous colonies (most of the Asian and African countries) during the colonial period and the ramification of their relation in the future after the fall of the empire starting with the second half of the twentieth century. It is a decolonization theory. One of its fundamental concerns is the previous colonies and their predicaments as a ramification of their historical subjugation and prolong denial to them the real idea of their history and civilization as a colonial administrative strategy. The “postcolonial” as an adjective is a problematic term. As the basic and converging informant, it is being used across array of ideas like postcolonial, postcolonialism, postcolonial literature, postcolonial studies and postcolonial theory intending to suggest epistemological distinctions between the variables in reference, which also implies inadequacy of them in accommodating the episteme they bear. This is already an indication that the term is self-contradictory. The term is informed by two main theoretical developments in the twentieth century: Deconstruction as discussed above and Marxism towards which we will reflect soon. Thus, the post-colonialism can be understood as an overlapped theory that denies the western canonical knowledge as absolute on one hand and therefore looks for its counterpart in the non-west and considers the literature as a discourse that concerns larger social structures which in-house the counterparts beyond its textual dimension. Simply put, this is a theory that deconstructs the assumed significance of accepted knowledge systems to give it a more social relevance, the west and the east being the immediate areas of engagement. But before further engagement with the postcolonial theories, it is important to understand the concept of the term “postcolonial” first. The use of “post” as prefix to the term “colonial” complicates its meaning. Andrew Bennet and Nicholas Royle in *Introduction to Literature, Criticism and Theory* (2008) observe that the terms ““post-...concerned with what comes *after* or continues to haunt the colony (Bennet, 215 emphases added)” which in a way clears a one-dimensional course of postcolonialism. While in some other critics the “what comes *after*”, the time period can be seen regressing until the beginning of the colonialism and fluctuating between its beginning, through and end. Accordingly, Kerstin W. Shands “Postcoloniality might be defined as a time and mindset occurring after the historical time of colonialism, a time when the colonial, decolonializing, and postcolonial processes and effects can be expressed and examined in literary and political narratives” (Shands 9). In this observation the terms get a retrograde valency that senses both before and after time of “colony.” Yet it is still a narrow understanding limited to only literary and political narratives. Other critics contest the take and try to understand it from a wider perspective. Bill Ashcroft, Gareth Griffiths and Helen Tiffin, for instance, in *Post-colonial Studies: The Key Concepts* (2000) try to understand the term in terms of pre-colonial, colonial and post-independence cultures. For them postcolonialism is a cultural movement: The simpler sense of the ‘post’ as meaning ‘after ‘colonialism has been contested by a more elaborate understanding of the working of post-colonial cultures which stresses the articulations between and across the politically defined historical periods, of *precolonial*, colonial and post-independence cultures (Ashcroft ,169). Recourse to history on the one hand and flowing with it on the other, then confront the postcolonialism with two problematic uniting in a paradox. The first or the going with the course of history suggests a chronological problematic; or a problem that concerns a particular time. In this sense the postcolonial or postcolonialism is a fact. The second which recognizes and negotiates with the history suggests an ideological problematic. In other words, the terms here mean an idea. It can be supplemented with the fact that the predominant idea of native as “other” or “subjugated” and “exploited” figure and the colonizer as its master can be equally found

operational even in the pre-colonial texts like Shakespeare's *The Tempest*. In the play Prospero, the protagonist, like the European colonizers, lands on an Island far away into the sea. The land belongs to Caliban who is projected as a dehumanized creature; partly human partly brute. Prospero usurps the island, as in the colonial context, and claims his superiority over Caliban, and as in a colonial relationship, makes him work for his selfish interest. Likewise, the colonial text *Heart of Darkness* by Joseph Conrad is an ideological discovery of Africa as "dark" and therefore uncivilized and barbaric, the predominant colonial conviction. What can be inferred then is that the terms seem to demonstrate their function somewhere in between the paradox of historical accuracy and their ideological tradition, trying to negotiate between the "precolonial," "colonial" and "after" colonial time and mindset. Along with the conflicting definitions, a good number of postcolonial theories have appeared in higher academia offering different perspectives to look into the paradox of the postcolonial relationship. The theories have formative influence from the classic work *Orientalism* (1978). Orientalism, according to Said, "can be discussed and analyzed as the corporate institution for dealing with the Orient-dealing with it by making statements about it, authorizing views of it, describing it, by teaching it, settling it, ruling over it: in short, Orientalism as a Western style for dominating, restructuring, and having authority over the Orient" (Said 03) through the colonial period and beyond. In other words, it is a cultural imperialism; it is the otherization of the orient and orient culture. When it involves the cultural imperialism, it also involves ideology of the dominating culture and its hegemony over the dominated, the orient. Therefore, the postcolonial studies also overlap with the neo-Marxism particularly with Louis Althusser and Antonio Gramsci, which deserve a brief elaboration here first before deviating into the theories. The take of Said in *Orientalism* triggers an exigency to inevitably revisit the construction of the orient through discourse analysis with an aim to reform the damage done, and accordingly a plethora of postcolonial theories have emerged and been practised as demonstrative models of the revision. Bill Ashcroft, Gareth Griffiths, and Helen Tiffin have categorized context specific indigenous revisionary models and their modus operandi in their seminal book *The Empire Writes Back* (1989), whose exploration deserves attention next. In the fourth chapter 'Theory at the Crossroads: Indigenous theory and post-colonial reading' the writers explore the working models of indigenous theory in the context of India, Africa, Caribbean and the settler colonies whose critical implementation would mean decolonization of the Eurocentric perspectives. The native traditions have "diglossic oral cultures" in which bilingualism has been strongly established. So the writers have a conviction that they have a huge potentiality of critical concepts from which a modern native critical theory can be designed. In the Indian context, they trace a native critical tradition in Sanskrit from 200 B.C. to 1780 A.D and other vernacular literatures like Tamil and Urdu: The earliest extant work of Indian criticism in Sanskrit, the *Natya Shastra of Bharata*, dates from c. 200 B.C. and there followed an unbroken tradition of commentary for some two thousand years to the work of Jagannatha (c. AD 1780). Literatures in other languages, such as Tamil and Urdu, also have extensive and ancient critical traditions (Ashcroft 116).

They also consider the attempt of the Indian critic like K. Krishnamoorthy^{iv} to see the possibility of use of Indian classical concept of "rasa," "dhvani" and "alankara" (suggestion, emotion and rhetoric) against the imported concepts like ambiguity, symbol, images etc, whose concern is to give a sense of Indianess to mode of expression, as a model of decolonization. The writers draw upon the idea of "Negritude" popularized by Aimé Césaire and the idea of the native communitarian African society by Leopold Senghor^v, to emphasize on a unique African characteristic, "a specific black African nature and psychology ..." (Ashcroft 122) and African way of community life. The concept is one of the earliest decisive ideas in the formation of Black consciousness and shaping the theories of "black literature" that had been suppressed and denied for centuries by the colonization. The writers see the future of Black literature in the concept which if endorsed with momentum would also mean decolonization. They also consider Frantz Fanon. Fanon, according to them, analyses the psychological and sociological consequence of colonization that creates the colonial dichotomy (colonizer-colonized) propagated through the colonial discourse in paired oppositions such as

“good–evil; true–false; white–black, in which the primary sign is axiomatically privileged in the discourse of the colonial relationship” (Ashcroft 124). But the same dichotomy can be used as a launching-pad for revisionary narratives with an aim to free the disabling position. An attempt to create a national literary history in every nation is also an attempt to establish an independent identity. This has not only happened in the previous colonies from where the masters eventually and literally retreated but also in the colonies where they settled and became dominant forever. These settler colonies- the United States, Canada, Australia and New-Zealand-attempt detachment as freedom from their originary legacy, unlike India and Africa where attempts are made to reconstruct the identity. The critics find in the early attempts by the writers of these colonies a common aspiration for detachment and in the later developments, the New Criticism as a theoretical tool. The reference is to the writers like Emerson (in America), Marcus Clarke^{vi} (in Australia) and Major Richardson^{vii} (in Canada) whose attempts were to create native scholars of native subject matter. The critics thus sum up the New Criticism, which considers nothing outside the text for interpretation, as the theoretical model to alienate a text from the extrinsic influence of writer’s background, reader’s choice, social dynamics and historical elements: In the early stages of settlement and national assertion there were, in the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada, concerted calls for a ‘native literature’ and ‘native’ critical tools with which to assess it...The advent of New Criticism in these areas ...can be seen as a major development in the critical self-awareness of these literatures (Ashcroft, 138).

What remains for interpretation after alienating the outside in the New Criticism then is an independent text whose task in the settler colonies is to consider every little bit of native, like the leaf of grass in Whitman which otherwise is negligible, as a subject having poetic potential. The politics of the consideration is to divert human mind towards both indigenous thinking and writing to get psychological freedom from the European legacy in order to initiate a national literary and critical history. Indian, African and Settler Colonies’ theoretical stances, however, are not appropriate for Naipaul throughout his career. He is in no position to go for something native and pristine as an alternative to the colonial model. There is no direct reference to Naipaul in the theoretical engagement of text in the Caribbean situation. But what he is obliged to opt in the context of Caribbean islands, therefore, is in the line of the critics like Edward Kamau Birthwaite who propounds for a Caribbean situation specific model that he calls ‘creolization.’ Unlike India, Africa and Settler Colonies’ the context of Caribbean Islands for a revisionary model is very complex. The aborigines (Caribs and Arawaks) were annihilated, unlike the natives in India and Africa, by the colonial domination and the islands gradually got creolized. The creolization already implies the presence of the European element too. Therefore, in the total absence of an aborigine culture and history, the origin of an indigenous critical decolonization model is difficult to think about and make operational. However, Edward Kamau Birthwaite, the Barbadian poet and academic, attempts a negotiation so that an indigenous theory of creolization can be initiated. According to Ashcroft, Birthwaite emphasizes on a “cross-cultural time-space dynamic” which implies a relation to land, place and people: “Creolization is a cultural action based upon the ‘stimulus–response’ of individuals to their environment and, within culturally discrete white–black groups, to each other” (Ashcroft 146). This gives a critical course to Caribbean writings and a sense of freedom from getting annihilation from the continuous assault of the postcolonial imperial cultural legacy. Unlike Ashcroft, critic like Homi K. Bhabha is interested in theorizing the postcolonial culture in general as a paradoxical phenomenon of the modern world that Naipaul also shares. The critic Inder Manjit Singh has observed that the ideas of Bhabha, like “colonialist experience... [and] colonial mimicry...are relevant to Naipaul’s fiction and other works” (Singh, 45) too and has tried to understand them in relation to Naipaul in his book *V.S. Naipaul* (2002). The major thrust of Bhabha in *The Location of Culture* is the unconventional understanding of the postcolonial, postmodern culture as a phenomenon “beyond” their borders. Postcolonial culture for him does not exist in a sequence with the past and its present. Rather, it is comprised of something that lies beyond their borders; it is

a place where “something begins its presencing” (Bhaba 5). In other words, he sees modern culture as a broad spectrum from which arrays of ideas like “history of postcolonial migration, the narratives of cultural and political diaspora...the poetics of exile, the grim prose of political and economic refugees” (Bhaba 5) mark the presencing of their beginning; they do not exist as the past-present continuum; the past exists as a necessity of life and not merely as a “nostalgia.” There are erasures, breaks and interruptions; the past is dropped if not necessary and entertained in between if it can really make a difference. In locating the culture and its manifestation in writing, Bhabha has often drawn Naipaul in his theories. In the fourth chapter ‘Of Mimicry and Man: The ambivalence of colonial discourse’ drawing upon the contention of Jacques Lacan in which he claims that the effect of mimicry is “camouflage”, a strategic practice in human warfare, meaning a truth designed to get mottled against a mottled background, Bhabha claims that colonial discourse is “ambivalent”, a mnemonic gymnastic between wanting one thing and wanting its opposite too. It implies that the colonial discourse has strategically created the colonial “other” of the imperial “master” which mottles with, or mimics, its background and thus disturbs the relation between east and the west. Mimicry is a “menace” for both. It’s so in the sense that being ambivalent it not only destroys the real essence of the “other” but also always already “disrupts” the colonial desire for its creation which ultimately loses its representational purpose; in spite of the intention of creating a compliant and loyal subject, the subject it creates is never far from mockery. According to Bhabha, the desire is “narcissistic;” it is a death-trap for both. He also theorizes the colonial mimicry as “metonymy of presence” (Bhabha, 89) which implies that the mimicry partially but paradoxically presences both the authorial presence and the cultural transformation of the “other” at the same time. There is only “partial representation...of the colonial object” in mimicry and the authorized legacy of the same has been manifested in the works of the postcolonial writers in the line of descent of whom Naipaul is one of them: The menace of mimicry is its double vision which in disclosing the ambivalence of colonial discourse also disrupts its authority. And it is a double vision that is a result of what I’ve described as the partial representation/recognition of the colonial object. Grant’s colonial as partial imitator, Macaulay’s translator, and Naipaul’s colonial politician as play-actor... these are the appropriate objects of a colonialist chain of command, authorized versions of otherness (Bhabha 88). Cataloguing Naipaul with Grant and Macaulay, the colonial scholars who proposed a fractured Indian as the colonial subject of strategic importance whose nature should be “... Indian in blood and colour, but English in tastes”, compliant and loyal, in the words of Macaulay as quoted by Bhabha, Naipaul has been seen as following the same line of “descent.” However, the mimicry in Naipaul is not a strategic imperative as in Grant and Macaulay, nor there is any celebration of it but there are realizations of its “menace” at a certain point of maturity. The mockery at least at some points of time gets evaporated surfacing its reality. The following two observations, for instance, from Ralph Singh, the protagonist in *The Mimic Men* can witness this truth. The first is his feeling of his own place, Isabella, the colonial opinion of the “other” vehicle through a mimic man; a state of condemning self, a mockery. He expresses his initial feeling about his place: “And I had a vision of...us shipwrecked and lost, alien and degenerate, the last of our race in this island, among collapsed trees and sand, so smooth where no one had walked on it” (Naipaul 1967: 195). The second is the realization of the limit of mimicry, the universality of the former, no sooner he lands in England in an attempt to get freedom from his circumstance. He says, “But even as I tried to put words to what I felt, I knew that my own journey, scarcely begun, had ended in the shipwreck which all my life I had sought to avoid” (Naipaul 1976: 10). Therefore, in Naipaul, developing with Bhabha, the paradox of mimicry is not always the “metonymy of presence”; rather it is also an escape from it. What gets demonstrated is that in the first observation, the psychology of a native is camouflaged by the psychology of a colonialist. But in the second, the camouflage gets stripped off. Bhabha sees mimicry also as the suicide of the ambivalent colonial discourse at its very, strategic, origin. This theory itself is the decolonization of the colonial “other.”

While there are critics like Ngugi wa Thiong'o who believe in decolonization of mind through replacement of western language, particularly English, by Africans as medium of literary expression. His theory of decolonization originates in the following premise. Thiong'o believes that language has dual character; a means of communication and carrier of culture. He observes that in the Scandinavian countries [Denmark, Norway, Finland and Sweden] English is a means of communication with foreigners and it is not the carrier of their culture. For culture related record and expression, the Scandinavians switch on to their native tongue. Whereas, for English/British English is both a means of expression and cultural carrier. Thiong'o goes up to the extent of saying that, in the process of western colonization "Bullet was the means of the physical subjugation. Language was the means of the spiritual subjugation" (Thiong'o 09), which has become an established agency of literary expression, fiction and theatre, in many of the native writers. Thus, he questions the use of foreign language, specifically English, as an authentic, appropriate and representative medium of native literary expression and with this advocates its replacement with African tongue as decolonization from the spiritual subjugation: Why, we may, ask, should an African writer, or any writer, become so obsessed by taking from his mother-tongue to enrich other tongues? Why should he see it as his particular mission? We never asked ourselves: how can we enrich our languages? ... Why not have Balzac, Tolstoy, Sholokov, Brecht, Lu Hsiang-shan, Pablo Neruda, H.C. Anderson, Kim Chi Ha, Marx, Lenin, Albert Einstein, Galileo, Aeschylus, Aristotle and Plato in African languages? And why not create literary monuments in our own languages..." (Thiong'o 08).

There is an intense desire to remember and recall the native past as new beginning. Yet, in the same African literary platform there are others who advocate the same foreign tongue with certain adaptation as the affective literary agency. The following from Achebe, quoted by Thiong'o himself, may close his decolonization theory giving the general African decolonization perspective a forked bent. Achebe thus opines: I feel that the English language will be able to carry the weight of my African experience. But it will have to be a new English, still in full communion with its ancestral home but altered to suit new African surroundings (Thiong'o 08). There is a desire to forget the past for a new beginning. The debate is, as Fauzia Mustafa observes, on the "possible paradoxes of postcolonial literature - namely, the disjunction between the materiality of language and the materiality of history" (Mustafa, 219), the possible incompatibility between English as the medium of expression of the local histories that every postcolonial writer including Naipaul encounters. But unlike Thiong'o or Achebe, Naipaul neither has native language as an alternative, therefore, nor can he have modification chance as decolonization. This implies he cannot be either with Thiong'o or Achebe, the two dominating perspectives in the postcolonial theoretical debate. What he can be is once again observed by Mustafa: "Naipaul's writing positions him as an Ariel figure" (Mustafa, 220), that is to say, like the figure of Ariel, the creative spirit in *The Tempest* who longs for freedom from the paradox of his enslavement by Prospero but carries on the command of his master passively without rebelling like Caliban, the "literary archetype" of most of the postcolonial writings, until he achieves it, Naipaul carries on with the English language for his ultimate recognition in the world literary platform. The critique of colonial history as decolonization has figured predominantly also in Frantz Fanon. In *The Wretched of the Earth* (1963) Fanon explores the psychological weapons, tools of violence, of the colonial history as part of subjugation means which eventually had terrible ramifications on natives in the French dominated Algeria in an attempt to, what he calls a, "start over a new history of man" (Frantz 238). He has marked several mental disorders in a series of case studies as markers of colonial violence as "triggering situation." Impotence, homicidal impulse, depressive disorder, murder of Europeans, paranoid delusion and suicidal behaviour, anxiety disorder, adjustment disorders, puerperal psychoses, clinical depression, anorexia nervosa, restlessness and psychosomatic disorders like stomach ulcer, renal colic, hypersomnia etc, to name a few, appeared in an increasing number not only in the natives but also in the European present in Algeria taking the shape of ultimate genocide, with far reaching political and economical ramifications of the West presence. Therefore, a history of decolonization of the Third World,

according to Fanon, will only become significant if it can decode the history making movements which supply its form and substance. Fanon thus draws the premises for decolonization of history: The Third World must start over a new history of man which takes account of not only the occasional prodigious theses maintained by Europe but also its crimes, the most heinous of which have been committed at the very heart of man, the pathological dismembering of his functions and the erosion of his unity, and the context of the community, the fracture, the stratification, the bloody tensions fed by class, and finally, on the immense scale of humanity, the racial hatred, slavery exploitation and, above all, the bloodless genocide whereby one and a half billion men have been written off (Fanon 238). While Fanonism relies on the exploration of crimes of colonialism in its extreme diversities as decolonization, there are critics like Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak for whom there are aprioris to crime as decolonization models. For her the decolonization should begin with the critique of the Western ideology which shaped and nurtured the colonial projects. Her critique of the Western reason, the Western knowledge system, as a desire to conserve the 'subject' of the West for power suggests a nexus between desire, power and subjectivity; a desire for subjectivity for power and the power for economic interest that found its application in colonialism. Also, her critique of Western racism can be read as a very sensitive deconstructive model of decolonization. In the seminal essay 'Can the Subaltern Speak?' she concentrates on a dialogue between Michel Foucault and Gilles Deleuze in reference to intellectual and power and in the meantime other theorist Derrida too suffers interpretation. According to Spivak, Foucault and Deleuze are propelled by the French poststructuralist contribution that "that intellectuals must attempt to disclose and know the discourse of society's Other" (Spivak 66). The opinion, the appeal to 'disclose', already suggests that the Western knowledge system believes in its "other" counterpart as inevitable and makes imperative for the intellectuals to have its knowledge. According to Spivak, the understanding of the 'other' by the intellectuals who seem to be the faithful legacy of the system in the meantime has 'schematized' its discourse entirely obliterating its textuality; it has been made non-referential denying its signifying potentialities. And in the process, sustained attempts have been made by the western intellectuals to mechanize and legalize its otherwise complicated social relationships. The following may be cited as examples: Foucault declares that "...my problem isn't a linguistic one" (Spivak 75); Deleuze opines that "A theory is like a box of tools, nothing to do with signifier" (Spivak 70) and Derrida emphasizes on the loss of origin of signifier and signified and suspended centrality of reference [which trigger many of the poststructuralist social theories in the twentieth century]. In all the opinions a consistent and strategic attempt has been made to conceal or forget the textuality of the knowledge system that constitutes the 'Other'. Spivak thus sums up:

...in the constitution of that Other of Europe, great care was taken to obliterate the textual ingredients with which such a subject could cathect, could occupy (invest?) its itinerary -not only by ideological and scientific production, but also by the institution of the law (Spivak 75).

Eventually, this mysterious figure totally stripped of potentialities is made to represent the colonial 'Other' in its complicated subaltern social relationship with the colonizer. In other words, the 'Other' at its origin is the part of the Western knowledge system itself but swiftly catered throughout the colonial history of subjugation as economics and power imperative to represent the colonized. Therefore, opines Spivak, for the understanding of the complicated and micro social relations between the colonial 'Other' and its creator, unlike the philosophers in reference, one must "move towards theories of ideology-of subject formations" (Spivak 74). Decolonization in this sense means to explore the role and strategy of the larger social structures as agency behind the purpose of the formation of the 'Other' in which economic factor has always remained a "final determinant." In this sense, the decolonization will imply a critique of history of formative ideology. Unless the formative ideology is put to scrutiny, the "re-presentation" of the 'Other' will never take shape and hence it will not be able to speak. Yet in 'Echo', in her socialist-feminist bent of reading Spivak turns against the racial dimension of the Western canon that designs 'Other' in terms of women and people beyond the specificity of the western culture. Immediate reaction comes from her reading of Ovid's

story of Echo and Narcissus (in *Metamorphoses*), Freud's Narcissus theory (in "On Narcissism: An Introduction") and continuation of the same in Christopher Lasch^{viii} (in *The Culture of Narcissism*). Richest instance of narcissism, according to her, in Freud are drawn from women. Further, Freud extends his instantiations of Narcissism in "primitive people," meaning people beyond the specificity of Western culture. Spivak quotes from him: "this extension of the libido theory receives reinforcement from our observations and views [speculations?] on the mental life of children and primitive peoples" (Spivak 21). The issue with the claim is that how and why it is possible, or what is the drive, for people like Freud from a privileged place to draw upon people from quite a distant origin and unprivileged condition. Spivak even finds a "curious" parallel in the intention of Ovid and Freud in their purpose. Ovid in *Metamorphoses* begins "My mind is bent to tell of bodies changed into new forms." (Spivak 21) and Freud in "On Narcissism" declares at the outset that "I am replacing the special chemical substances...by special psychical forces" (Spivak 21). Thus drawing a centrality of intention in the narcissus theory in the discourse of Ovid, Freud and Lash, she concludes that the canon was under an "offensive" of racial exigency that targets the 'Other'-women and the "primitive" people: "I am remarking that the scientific basis that Freud needs is deeply marked by a rather offensive sort of casual racism" (Spivak 21). The postcolonial theoretical platform is yet not free from confronting self reflection; there are opinions that make the theories recoil back to themselves. There are developments that question the parameters of the theoretical analysis. There are contentions that the postcolonial perspective with its revenge motive has done more damage than favour to the "Other" in the sense that the motive already begins with the acceptance of the "otherness"; attempt to negate "otherness", philosophically speaking, also means already acceptance of what is being negated. In this sense the perspective, obliquely though, still defends the colonialism and in the meantime, it rarely considers the theoretical self-reliance of the non-West episteme. While trying to deconstruct the Western cannon it ends being more exposed; what is considered to be marginal in the East still remains as it is. One of the pioneers in this line of thought, Leela Gandhi, thus finds suicidal holes in the perspectives:

...what postcolonialism fails to recognise is that what counts as 'marginal' in relation to the West has often been central and foundational in the non-West. Thus, while it may be revolutionary to teach Gandhi as political theory in the Anglo-American academy, he is, and has always been, canonical in the India. Despite its good intentions, then postcolonialism continues to render non-Western knowledge and culture as 'other'... (Gandhi, 'Preface' ix-x). There are even questions on the methods of the theories in which the Western canonical texts (as in Said, Spivak) have remained the target of critical assaults while trying to draw the genealogy of the ideological formation/making of the colonies. These texts formed in and by the West are cited by them as the embeded examples of both the dominating and the dominated ideologies and their colonial implications. The question is, can these texts originating entirely from the colonial authority without having any substantial engagement in the heterogeneous cultural experience of the colonized displace the "white mythology"? Thus, Banita Parry questions, substantiating the argument from Spivak and Bhaba, in whom she sees the "limitations of their different deconstructive practices" (Parry 19) which "constrain the development of a radical anti-colonial critique" (Parry19):

There is moreover a further political question to be asked of colonial discourse theory...can a practice [the theoretical discourse analysis] which is predominantly concerned with the text of colonial authority, which does not address itself to colonialism's culture and neglects to engage with its heterogeneous system of knowledge, produce, as it claims, a critique displacing the west's 'white mythology'? (Parry, 17). The complaint is against the theories getting more and more one dimensional focusing more on the Western canon which does not take into account the heterogeneity of the colonial culture. The theories tend to focus on the West instead the East which though might deconstruct the formative colonial ideology, do not thoroughly engage in exploring and promoting the potentiality of later as an alternative. Figuration of Darwin (as social Darwinism), Silvestre de Sacy and Ernest Renan^{ix} in *Orientalism* (1978), Derrida, Foucault, Delueze, Freud and Ovid in

Spivak as referential texts supplement the argument of Parry. The colonial authority figures overabundantly also in fiction, in Naipaul himself for instance. The 19th century French thinker Marcel Proust, for instance, has figured as a prime influence on his intuitive writing. In his *Noble Lecture* he thus hails Proust: "...he was a man trusting to his intuition...I have quoted these words before in other places. The reason is that they define I have gone about my business. I have trusted to intuition. I did it at the beginning. I do it even now" (Naipaul 2001, 02). Even in the fabric of his fictions, for instance in *A House for Mr. Biswas*, the Western thinkers have figured as inspiration. Mr. Biswas reads Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus^x. All the proponents in the contentions as established above, operate around the issues triggered by the dynamism of the West and the East during and after the colonial period. They seem to be operational for re-orientation of the world order ravaged by the colonialism, re-presenting the East in its essence as a contrary to their colonial representation. Colonialism is made accountable and it is thought to be completely a project of the Western culture. Yet, along the same theoretical line of descent there are interruptions which try to silent the entire theoretical voices making the colonial project equally a cultural enterprise of the East as it is of the West. Therefore, the postcolonial debate as long as it raises fingers on the West also questions itself. Critic Ashis Nandy is a prominent voice in the line who paradoxically assumes that the colonial culture is also a "shared culture", unlike its conventional understanding, which does not just origin and end at definite points of time like the Western colonialism. Thus, assuming this stand in *The Intimate Enemy* (1983) taking India as case study, he postulates the aim of his reading as:

...to define colonialism as a shared culture which may not always begin with the establishment of alien rule in a society and end with the departure of the alien rulers from the colony. The example...[is] that of India, where a colonial political economy began to operate seventy-five years before the full-blown ideology of British imperialism became dominant, and where thirty –five years after the formal ending of the Raj, the ideology of colonialism is still triumphant in many sectors of life (Nandy, 02).

The culture being shared, Nandy observes, and made operative as drive of the colonialism is however shaped in the West but too a large extend internalized and promoted by India, even by the classics. For instance, the modern concept of a child as "inferior" adult to be educated as contrast to "smaller version of adult", a "happy angel" in the convention, according to Nandy, is a seventeenth century European finding, a concept of the Protestant Ethics. In the new version the child is like a "blank slate" in which moral codes are to be written by elders; the child is "less productive and ethical" and "contaminated" by irresponsible human nature. It is the duty of the adults, who are thought to be morally potential, therefore to "save" this child. According to Nandy, colonialism picked up this idea of the moral education of the child and finds parallels between the child and primitivism and make them modus operandi of colonialism in India.

Yet, in India, unlike pre-Islamic worlds, the authority gets confronted. Straightforward labelling denouncing Indian civilisation (in front of which the European is a baby civilization) as inferior to European that needs education will be an unconvincing and futile attempt. Therefore, the empire develops two alternative theories: the rich ancient Indian civilization is "dead" and the present has nothing of its past richness; it's a "decrepit version" of the dead ideals which needs new education in the moral codes from a European adult. This creates a disjunction and eraser in the history of Indian civilization and the dislocated Indians were conditioned to believe in the new theories. The idea gets internalization in the Indian through the ideological writings of the people like Michael Mdhutan Dutt (1824-73). According to Nandy, in the epic *Meghnathbadh Kavya*, (a widely read epic on the story of the death of Meghnath, the son of Ravana) a Bengali epic, for instance Dutt, unprecedentedly, hails the demons as moral; Rama and Lakshmana are represented as feminine villains and Meghnatha as heroic, masculine, moral and just; the ancient allegorical figures of the virtue and the vice are ideologically altered. Bankimchandra does the same to Krishna. In 'Krsnacharitra'(1886), for instance the representation of Krishna is not "soft" and "child"; he does not adore Krishna as " child-god or as a playful" (Nandy, 23) as in the convention; for him the traits

of Krishna are “unacceptable to the new norms relating to sexuality, politics and social relationships” (Nandy 23). Further, Nandy also draws Swami Dayanand Saraswati (1824-83) and Swami Vivekananda (1863-1902) in the same internalizing trend. They hail past glory of Aryan India and held the “cultural regression of the Hindus was due to the loss of the original Aryan qualities which they shared with the Westerners” (Nandy 25). The imperative for invocation of the rich “dead” also obliquely proves already acceptance of the colonial theory and its promotion. All these can be seen as “...a direct response to the colonial situation” (Nandy 29). Therefore, what is ideologically internalized by the colonized in the colonial context is what the colonizers intended of their culture; therefore, the colonized has equal share in the colonization. The colonization is also equally internal; it also has space in the Indian “cosmology”:

...if there exists a prior endogenous West or a West with its own limited place in Indian cosmology, there is no reason why the Westerner should be seen as a total intruder or, for that matter, as the all-important intruder (Nandy 76).

Nandy at his extreme thus attempts to realign and relocate the origin of colonialism in the East itself.

FINDING :

It can be inferred that the ideas discussed above deviate from each other and thus can be melted down into a figure of paradox. This paradox can become a more appropriate framework in reading and understanding a postcolonial text. What figures in Derrida and Lacan is crucial in reading identity [of ‘other’] formation, unformation and re-formation paradox in a colonial context; Marxism gives social domain to the context; and the postcolonial theories which form intertextualities with the formers, nevertheless having a unanimous decolonization mission, are often seen at odd with each other’s claim. In the Postcolonial theories, Ashcroft and Ngugi stand for as a native alternative from the native practices. In the Africans like Achebe and Birthwaite the theory rests in a negotiation between the native and the foreign. Fanon sees decolonization in the exploration of the movements that mark colonial violence. In Bhabha the theory considers the postcolonial culture in general, without the distinction of East and West. Spivak is a critique of Western reason as decolonization. And the theorists like Gandhi and Parry see the limitation in all the preceding, whereas Ashis Nandy considers the colonialism an internal/native phenomenon as well.

CONCLUSION :

This awareness of the paradox, a theoretical disharmony - in philosophy, psychology, Marxism and postcolonial studies- will be imperatively crucial as informant in understanding a postcolonial writer like Naipaul. Deconstruction shall precaution us with the possibility of having multiple frames of paradox; Lacanian scheme of the psychoanalysis will keep on prompting us to consider the identity of the discursive world(India, Africa, Europe, Caribbeans, South America) that figures in the fiction of the postcolonial writer like Naipaul; Althusser and Gramsci with their discourse of ideology and hegemony will warn us to inevitably consider the fictions in their social intersection ; and the post-colonial theories, having formative influence from all the precedents, will situate this reading in the discursive post-colonial socio-cultural context as the background. In this sense the subject matter of a postcolonial text, as in the fictions of Naipaul, can be anticipated of being already always paradoxical in nature: having deconstructive, textual, social and discursive socio-cultural dimensions. This paradox, however, should not be understood as the ultimate framework for understanding a postcolonial text; it is rather its horizon.

END NOTES:

ⁱ Oxford online dictionary <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com> , Accessed 13th Jun.2018.

ⁱⁱ Oxford online dictionary <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com> , Accessed 13th Jun.2018.

ⁱⁱⁱ Oxford online dictionary <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com> , Accessed 13th Jun.2018.

- ^{iv} Reference to Krishnamoorthy, K. (1984) 'The all-time relevance of Bharata's literary Canons' in Narasimhaiah and Srinath 1984.
- ^v Aime Fernand David Cesaire, a Francophone and French Poet, the founder of the Negritude movement in Francophone literature; and Leopold Sedar Senghor a Senegalese poet and theoretician of Negritude
- ^{vi} Marcus Andrew Hislop Clarke, the 19th century English-borne Australian novelist, best known for the 1874 novel *For the Term of His Natural Life*.
- ^{vii} An early 19th century Canadian-borne British novelist.
- ^{viii} Robert Christopher Lash, the American social critic, a history professor at University of Rochester.
- ^{ix} Dominant 19th century orientalist: Sacy was an anthropologist and Renan a philologist
- ^x Marcus Aurelius was a second century stoic philosopher from Rome; Epictetus was first century Greek stoic philosopher.

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